

Etiological Factors of Non Communicable Diseases Pertaining to Pranvaha and Raktavaha Srotas

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Abstract—Non-communicable diseases are those which are not caused by infectious agents, these are the chronic diseases, which last for long periods. These are the major cause of adult mortality and morbidity worldwide. These diseases are identified by WHO as group 2 diseases -A category that aggregates the following conditions/ causes of death- Malignant neoplasia, Diabetes mellitus, endocrine disorders, respiratory diseases. According to WHO, there are four main types of non-communicable disease – cardiovascular diseases, chronic respiratory disease, cancers and diabetes. In Ayurveda, different types of nidana are mentioned which can be responsible for various diseases. Separate nidana are also mentioned according to different srotas. In Raktavaha strotodushhti nidana, aacharya Charak have mentioned “vidahiannapanani snighdhoshanani dravyanicha” i.e. intake of food and drink which is sharp and acidic in nature causes burning of natural smooth composition of rassa dhatu which results in formation of abnormal rakta dhatu and hence causes vitiation of raktavaha srotas. Like-wise in Pranvaha srotas dushti nidana it is mentioned that excessive indulgence of exercise and work out causes exhaustion and loss of normal smooth texture of pranvaha srotas. In modern science we can correlate vyadhis of these srotas with the cardiovascular and respiratory diseases on the resemblance with the symptoms.

Keywords—Nidana, srotas, srotodushhti, raktavaha srotas, pranvaha srotas.

I. INTRODUCTION

Non communicable disease is a medical condition or disease that is not caused by infectious agents¹ these are distinguished by their non infectious cause, not necessarily by their duration, though some chronic diseases of long duration can be caused by infections. Non Communicable diseases kill 40 million people each year equivalent to 70% of all deaths globally.²Each year, 15 million people die from a NCD between the ages of 30 and 60 years; over 80% of these premature deaths occur in low and middle income countries. A number of diseases come under the title Non Communicable diseases but there are mainly 4 groups of diseases in NCD – CVD, Cancers, Chronic respiratory diseases and diabetes.³In addition to these 4 main diseases, mental disorders are considered to be major contributors to the economic losses stemming from NCDs. NCDs are a serious threat to the global development agenda. These diseases are caused by a number of causes like, lack of physical activities, poor and unbalanced diet etc. In Ayurvedic text, exact term “Non Communicable

disease” is not mentioned but diseases which are not of infectious origin and of long duration can be considered under this title. It is mentioned by aacharyas that the diseases occur due to imbalance in the vata, pitta and kapha doshas. It is caused by different types of srotodushhti⁴. In ayurvedic text, different types of srotas have mentioned by a number of aacharyas.⁵These are prana, udaka, anna, rasa, rakta, mamsa, meda, asthi, majja, shukra, pureesha, sweda, mutravaha srotas.⁶ All vyadhis occurred by srotodushhti. Aacharya Charak has mentioned four types of srotodushhti which leads to different types of diseases.⁷

II. MATERIAL AND METHOD

In modern medicine, Non communicable diseases are those conditions that are usually not passed on from one affected person to other, but are caused as a direct result of life style changes and environmental factors. General causes of NCDs are lack of physical activities, poor and unbalanced diet, tobacco abuse, alcohol abuse which leaves people vulnerable to a host of diseases including lung disease, metabolic disorders and cancers. According to Ayurvedic system of medicine the diseases are caused by vitiation in tridoshas which leads to different types of srotodushhti which in turn produces diseases. Aacharya charak has mentioned thirteen types of srotas, pranvaha and raktavaha srotas are one among them. Four types of srotodushhti are also explained in the text. These are atipravriti, sanga, siragranthi and vimargagamna.

Pranvaha srotas are the channeled system which deals with functioning of vata thereto functioning related to respiration. Organs related to respiration are included in the pranvaha srotas. Their moola is Hridaya and Mahasrotas⁸. The causes of vitiation of pranvaha srotas are⁹

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“kshyaat sandharnat rokshyat vyayamat kshudhitya cha pranavahani dushyanti srotansyanyaishcha darunaity”

Kshya - Depletion of dhatus.

Sandharna- Suppression of natural urges

Raukshya- Dryness to the srotas due to continual intake of dry, harsh and preserved food items.

Vyayama- Excessive physical exercise leads to undue rapidity to respiration which causes stress and it causes exhaustion to respiratory organs.

Kshudha-long standing starvation causes *rasa dhatu* concentration leads to rendering imbalance of bodily fluid which weakens the *pranvaha srotas*.

Anya srotas dushti - Abnormality of the other system.

Kasa and *Tamaka shwasa* are two among those diseases which are mentioned under *Pranvaha Srotas vyadhi*. *Tamaka Shwasa* is caused by inhalation of dust and smoke, residing in cold atmosphere, intake of chilled water or cold beverages, excessive physical exercise and injury to vitals points of the body.¹⁰ Now-a-days, craze of smoking is increasing among people. Smoking is one among the leading causes of *Tamaka Shwasa*. In this disease the person suffers from attack of strenuous breathing which produces severe restlessness with the feeling of suffocation and frequent bouts of coughing with production of small sputum. On the basis of symptomatology, *Tamaka Shwasa* can be correlated with Bronchial asthma in modern science. *Kasa* is caused by accidental entry of food particles or foreign body inside the respiratory tract, intake of dried food items, inhalation of dust, mist and smoke.¹¹ In modern medicine *kasa* can be correlated with cough.

Raktavaha srotas is channeled system which deals with circulation of blood in required form to every system and thereto deals with nourishment of all the body system. Their *moola* is *yakrit* and *pleeha*. The causes of *raktavaha srotas* are¹²

“*Vidahanyapanani snigdhoishnani dravani cha raktavahini dushyanti bhajtam chatapanalo*”

Intake of food and drink, which are sharp and acidic in nature that causes burning of natural composition of *rasa dhatu* resulting in formation of abnormal *rakta dhatu* and hence causes vitiation of *raktavaha srotas*. Intake of fatty food, intake of excessively liquid food, excessive contact with the sun or heat. These all causes vitiation of *rakta dhatu* and further leads to *raktavaha srotas vyadhi*.

Kamala and *kushtha* are common diseases which come under *raktavaha srotas vyadhi*. *Kamala* is caused by excessive intake of dried, cold (by potency), hard to digest, sweet food contents, excessive physical exertion and restraining the natural urges. All these causes aggravation of *kapha* and *vata dosha*, *kapha* produces obstruction in the pathway of normal *pachaka pitta dosha*. Due to this normal surge of *pachaka pitta* obstructs and it saturates inside the *pittashaya*. Lack of *pachaka pitta* gives pale colour to the stool. Then spreading of vitiated *pitta dosha* to all over the body and eyes, skin, nails and urine becomes dark yellow in colour. *Kushtha* is caused by intake of incompatible food, suppression of natural urges like vomiting, drinking cold water immediately after contacting direct heat. These cause vitiation of *tridoshas* which cause weakness of *dushya* and leads to *kushtha* disease.

III. DISCUSSION

As told by different *aacharyas* imbalance in natural constituents of the body occurs due to repeated intake of causative/ etiological factors which in turn leads to *srotodushiti*. It is the main cause of production of diseases in

ayurvedic science of medicine. *Pranvaha srotas vyadhis* are caused by suppression of natural urges, excessive physical exertion, continual intake of dry, harsh and preserved food items. Continual uptake of following factors leads to exhaustion and loss of normal smooth texture of *pranvaha srotas* and finally production of different diseases. Likewise intake of adulterated liquor, intake of excessively salty, alkaline, sour, potently hot type of food, excessive contact with the sun or heat leads to vitiation of *raktavaha srotas*. This will leads to *raktavaha srotodushiti* which in turn causes different diseases in the body. As non Communicable Diseases are mainly divided into four main diseases- chronic respiratory diseases, cardiovascular diseases, cancers and diabetes so on the basis of etiological factors and symptomatology, *pranvaha* and *raktavaha srotas vyadhis* can be correlated with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Removal of causative factors is helpful in cure of the diseases and life style modification will be helpful in maintaining the normal constituent of body and prevention of the diseases.

IV. CONCLUSION

Non communicable diseases can be correlated to diseases of long duration which are of non-infectious origin. As these are caused by change in life style, excessive indulgence with tobacco and alcohol so life style modification can be helpful in prevention of NCDs. According to *Ayurveda* repeated acceptance of *nidana* leads to vitiation of *tridosha*. Imbalance in natural components of body leads to formation of ailments in different ways. These diseases if treated timely are *sadhya* (easy to cure) and if these are left untreated they become chronic in nature and difficult to cure. As NCDs are diseases of long duration with non infective origin and mainly divided in four groups- chronic respiratory diseases, cardiovascular diseases, diabetes and cancers so, on the basis of symptomatology and etiological factors diseases of *Pranvaha* and *raktavaha srotas* can be correlated with respiratory and cardiovascular diseases in modern medicine.

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